

DESIGNING A PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSON THROUGH GENDER CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: In this article, the problem of organizing a physical education class at school based on the tender approach is addressed. It is shown that the actualization of gender roles of schoolchildren requires the creation of special conditions that reinforce stereotypes of male and female behavior. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the difference in the motives of physical education of boys and girls. The data of experimental works on the formation of motor creativity in schoolchildren in the organization of the educational process based on the gender characteristics of students are presented.

Key words: gender approach, gender roles, physical culture, gender identity, educational system.

Today, the issue of implementing a tender approach to education and upbringing of the young generation is more acute than ever. And this is not a coincidence. The disappearance of the natural, natural differences between men and women worries the public, and this, in turn, leads to disruptions in the interaction of the sexes, the alignment and sometimes the change of the individual's gender roles.

The actualization of the tender role of the person requires the teacher to create conditions that strengthen the stereotypes of male and female behavior in schoolchildren. The most obvious tender characteristics are manifested in the implementation of physical activity, therefore, the methodological basis for designing the physical education process at school should be the tender approach.

Based on the physical education lesson, the tender approach, taking into account the gender characteristics of the subjects of the educational process, it is necessary to actualize the tender roles of the individual, to form the understanding and awareness of the latter about the purpose of men and women in society.

Such an organization of the educational process requires the teacher to have knowledge of the gender characteristics of schoolchildren, the need to distinguish between gender roles and conduct separate lessons on physical education. It is known that boys have a higher need for physical activity than girls. Boys want to be strong, courageous, durable, girls are more emotional and they feel a more specific need for the aesthetic direction of the physical education lesson. Exercise motivations also vary.

According to psychologists, boys are often interested in one way or another similar to an already existing field of interest, while girls have a radical novelty in relation to their usual activities. At the same time, boys are interested in things that deepen and develop existing skills, and girls prefer activities that meet their personal interests and needs at the moment.

It becomes clear why both boys and girls are less interested in physical culture in mixed classes, and both are unable to satisfy their physical needs in a class focused on an average

asexual subject. As a result, only 40% of schoolchildren participate in physical education classes as intended, wanting to have good physical development. At the same time, boys understand it as developing motor qualities, and girls as improving their aesthetic appearance: figures, walking, etc. Girls' lack of interest in physical culture, in particular, is due to the fact that the direction and requirements of these activities are more in line with the values of boys. This conclusion is confirmed by the data of other authors who studied the reasons for attending physical education classes of schoolchildren.

Physical culture, which is a part of general culture, has its own characteristics and regulatory mechanisms unique to it. Many authors say that this social change of the human body, its physical condition, on the one hand, on the other, affects the development of the individual, shapes his value relationships, life strategy, way of thinking and worldview in general.

Physical education activities, according to V. A. Pegov, include performance and creative aspects. The highest level of acquaintance with physical culture is manifested in the art of self-expression through physical movements. Art is unimaginable without creativity, without creativity it is unthinkable to develop the values of physical education and the content of physical education. Psychologists show in their works that collective creative activity is the most effective. Therefore, the teacher should inculcate values and realize the content of physical education with his students, in creative collaboration, cooperation, co-creation, sympathy for the results of joint activities. A physical education teacher has real opportunities to organize such activities.

As part of the training, it can be a plot, game, music lessons using the method of circle exercises, rhythmic gymnastics, national games, dances, etc. but the effectiveness of this activity depends on the teacher's lesson. The organization of cognitive activity depends on the ability to develop motor creativity in students based on a tender approach, taking into account the gender differences of children.

Creativity is the highest form of human activity, the essence of the human way of being in the world. It was A. Y. Ponomarev who considered creativity to be the main mechanism of personal development. The physical education lesson has all the conditions for the development of motor creativity in schoolchildren as a determinant of the creative development of the individual, at the same time, favorable conditions have been created for the renewal of tender roles, the tender identification of subjects of the educational process.

When organizing a physical education lesson aimed at developing motor creativity in schoolchildren, we relied on the tender characteristics of individuals, the natural physiological needs of children, the level of their physical development, and the difference in the mental bases of interest in boys and girls.

The 6th grade students of the general education school took part in the experiment. Physical education classes were held separately: girls trained in one gym, boys in another. Classes were held twice a week. The process of developing motor creativity in schoolchildren was carried out through successive interrelated stages: reproductive, normative and creative.

Creativity in the motor field includes the influence on the intellectual and motor functions of a person. At the same time, the relationship between thinking and activity is observed only if it is aimed at solving one problem.

In the lessons with the girls' contingent, special instrumental tasks were used for musical accompaniment, schoolchildren learned independently structured mini-complexes of

rhythmic gymnastics and had time for free improvisation to music. The teacher often changed the sets of general development exercises, which increased the emotional color of the lesson and introduced new elements.

Musical accompaniment is one of the most important factors of increasing creative activity for girls, emotional response to activities in class. Under the music, general development exercises, rhythmic gymnastics complexes, walking, running, etc. were carried out. they practiced to the music.

The different emotional reactions of man to the nature of music were known to the ancient Greeks. This requires the teacher to choose a specific musical program to stimulate muscle activity. Music affects a person as a rhythmic and emotional stimulus, therefore, the music chosen for physical exercises has a positive effect only if it matches the rhythmic, plot, age and physical characteristics of the students.

Such an approach did not have a significant positive effect on the boys during the lesson. The musical accompaniment did not interest them, and performing general development exercises under the music, on the contrary, hardened, caused some irritation and insecurity. They like to run, compete, play rather than perform various exercises to music. Therefore, in the classroom with children, accents are distributed a little differently. It included learning and predicting tactical combinations in various sports games, improving previously learned exercises, improving technical elements, and developing endurance, strength, and speed qualities.

In boys, it is the game and competition that causes a strong emotional reaction, where it should be noted that girls love to play and compete at this age. During the game, especially when playing sports, boys are ready to develop and implement tactical combinations, and if such a combination leads to a winning point, it becomes the pride of its developer and the author himself becomes the subject of respect from other participants of the game. Assembling tactical combinations, playing is the most effective factor in the development of motor and mental creativity in schoolchildren - boys. Achievements in this type of activity significantly increase self-esteem and create a positive emotional background, increase activity and interest in physical education classes among schoolchildren.

The analysis of experimental works allowed to determine the characteristics of the manifestation of mental and motor creativity in girls and boys. Thus, girls show a high level of creativity in improving various motor activities under musical accompaniment, and boys in motor activities of a playful nature.

Different levels of motivation for educational activities were found in boys and girls. Girls are more able to deal with the process of activity itself, boys are often interested if it has a clear direction. Girls, as a rule, if possible, try to master everything that is taught to them, boys - try to be selective from the beginning. Girls are often interested in activities that are radically new to them, while boys are ready to engage in things that are similar to their already formed areas of interest.

The development of creative abilities of schoolchildren in the course of educational activities in a comprehensive school leads to significant changes in the indicators of children's creative activity: it increases interest in physical education activities, develops initiative and independence, students' cognitive abilities and ensures the realization of creative potential at a high level. In addition, the orientation of the lesson to the development of creative potential in the motor field helps to develop the personal qualities of schoolchildren: responsibility,

self-organization, initiative, knowledge and motor activity, self-control, endurance, perseverance in achieving the goal and the tool ensures the formation of creative experience. Targeted work on the development of the creative potential of schoolchildren in the field of motor, undoubtedly, in the educational process, relying on the tender approach, the physiological, physical, psychological characteristics of the development of children of a certain age group, contribute to the tender identification of schoolchildren in the lesson. Can be very effective in creating conditions that encourage stereotypes.

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